

<p>About Conducting Research on the Subject of Ornithological Terms in Uzbek Language</p>		<p>Linguistics</p> <p>Keywords: have the knowledge of the Uzbek Language, Uzbek linguists, the lexical system of the Uzbek language, semantic field, etymology, zoonims, ornithonims.</p>
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<p>Abstract</p> <p>In this article there are given some data about a brief observation of studying lexical system of the Uzbek language, the names of scientists, whose efforts have helped arouse opportunities of the language. This article thoroughly highlights several studies done in the field of lexical system, especially semantic features of terms relating to food, clothes and architecture. The author of this article states that ornithological terms which are considered as a part of zoonims, can be the subject of special investigation for linguists. And also author studied the some birds' names are not included in literary language or their literary norms are not assigned clearly for not having been studied thoroughly.</p>		

There have been great advances in the branch of lexicology and etymology of the Uzbek language since the Independence of Uzbekistan was proclaimed. It is considered a great success of Uzbek onomastics publishing books “The meanings of Uzbek names” by E. Begmatov, which came into existence as a result of his thorough study for many years and “The definition of Uzbek onomastic terms” by E. Begmatov and N. Uluqov (in 2006) and bibliography named “Onomastics of the Uzbek language” (in 2008). It has been a special event not only in the Uzbek language but in the Turkish language system publishing the book “Fundamentals of systematic lexicology of the Uzbek language” by R. Rasulov (Nurmanov A., 2012, 34-41).

Such achievements have been gained in the field of etymology in linguistics. For example, “Etymological dictionary of the Uzbek language” which constitutes three parts (whose author is professor Rahmatullaev Sh) was announced to have been published in 2000-2009. It is an urgent matter for our linguists to create a perfect etymological dictionary of the language in the near future.

“Monolingual dictionary of the Uzbek language” which was published in 2006-2008 in 5 tomes has a significant value in Uzbek lexicography. (By Sul-tonmurod Olim, in 2008: Mahmudov N., in 2008; Mahmudov N., in 2008, 79-85; Madvaliev A., in 2008 and so on)

There have been done a lot of studies in the field of terminology in Uzbek linguistics. For example several monographs have been written by investigating terms used in art, architecture, cookery and for naming clothes. This can be also illustrated with dissertations on terminology done by some scientists such as S. Ibragimov, N. Mamatov, H. Jamolkhonov, R. Doniyorov, N. Hotamov, O. Ramazonova, T. Tursunova, M. Asomiddinova, A. Juraboev, J. Dustmuhammedov, N. Kosimov, H. Shamsiddinov, A. Madvaliev, E. Shoahmedov, Yu. Eshonkulov, H. Dadaboev, I. Yuldoshev, A. Kosimov, O. Kurbonov, T. Numonov, T. Khujamberdiev, M. Buronov, T. Urinov, H. Bakaeva, K. Sapoev, S. Azizov, S. Usmonov, K. Khurramav, Kh. Jabborov, Z. Husainova.

Only since 2000, monographs and dissertations on terminology have been done studying terms used in jewelry (by I. Pardaeva), woodworking (by M. Ahatova), in law (by G. Gulomova), irrigation (by Kh. Jabborov), cattle-breeding (by O. Urinova) and names of meals in Uzbek dialects spoken in Karakalpakstan (by M. Khudayarova). The development of Uzbek scientific terminology can be seen through dissertations done on themes “Scientific-theoretical issues of expressing juridical norms in the Uzbek language” by Sh. Kuchimov in 2004, “Uzbek terminology in the field of creating books: its formation, development and arrangement” by I. Yuldashev (Yuldashev I. J., in 2005, 8-37), “Systems analysis of lexicons of any special branch” by M. Abdiev (Abdiev M., in 2005, 7-41) and monographs which were written based on these dissertations such as “Lexicon of the Uzbek language used in Irrigation” (in 2004) and “Lexical-notional peculiarities of the lexis Water in the Uzbek language ” (in 2005) by Kh. Jabborov.

Some research studies analyzing animal names in Uzbek linguistics have been carried out. It should not be forgotten that the lexis “animal” has a wider meaning than the lexes “zoonim” and “ornithonim” and can be used instead of those two lexes. The term “zoonim” has a specific meaning expressing mammals and its general meaning states all the animal world including living and dead things on the contrary to plants. From this point of view, it can include the world of birds in some cases. Therefore, in some research studies analysing animal names, you can notice that birds` names are mentioned. Since the early days of Turkish nations animal names including zoonims and ornithonims have been a significant part of the lexicology of these languages. All aspects of Turkish nations` lifestyle can be understood perfectly through zoonims. (Musaev, K.M., in 1975, 52-53)

Linguists have been interested in animal names for a long time. For instance, T. Urinov conducts a dissertation on the theme: “Terminology in cattle-breeding in the Uzbek language ” in 1964. The author of this work is aware of terms in cattle-breeding, so he wanted some technical terms as “rotational pump” and “waterpipe with belt” to be used as terms of cattle-breeding. It is not too perfect one to be named “From the resources of Kashkadaryo region”, because terms like “chinnoq”, dutorbuyin”, ”sovlik”(sheep), kuchkor” (ram),”kuzi”(lamb) are used in other territories of our country.(T. Urinov, 1964, 7-12). Then the dissertation was done on the theme: ”Terms in cattle-breeding in Uzbek dialects spoken in Karakalpakstan” by M. Buranov. In this work some lexes which are used to call and expel sheep and goats as ”kur-kur”, “goch-goch”,”hov-hov” are studied as shepherding terms (Buranov M.,1972,6-14). The research done by T.Khujamberdiev on the theme: “Lexicon of the Uzbek language relating to cattle-raising” (done based on the dialect of Fergana valley) is an important step to study lexes relating to cattle-breeding as well as birds` names and poultry raising. (Khujamberdiev T., 1975, 5-12). In this work the principle of distinguishing species from its common group. For example the researcher tried to identify the role and the usage of lexes ”yilki”(a horse-herder), “mol” (cattle), “hayvon” (animal), “darranda”, “parranda” (birds), “tovar” (goods) which are in a group “cattle”. In this work the terminological system relating to cattle-raising is learnt by dividing it into 15 small thematic groups considering the subject from the onomastic point of view. However, in this research work there is no exact

limit for the subject of terminological system. Although the main purpose of the research is to analyze the terms used in horse-breeding, you can notice some lexes relating to cattle-breeding, sheep-raising, goat-breeding and poultry. Moreover, there is no difference between zoonims and fitonims (plants` names) in some cases.

R. Kungurov states that several imitative words were formed by imitating the sounds of animals and illustrates his opinion by giving examples from fictions where such words are used as “urdak” (duck), “goz” (geese), “khuroz” (cock), “kaklik” (partridge), “bedana” (quail), “boykush” (owl), “gurak” (turtle-dove), “kaldirgoch” (swallow), “karkunak” (shrike), “bulbul” (nightingale), “turna” (crane). Then the work is concluded as “such words imitating the sound of birds might have been formed as a result of their actions. Some birds` names were taken from their sounds..... Such cases can be noticed in other languages”(Kungurov R., in 1966, 66-67).

R. Kungurov puts forward import concepts about compound ornithological terms which are formed as an adjective + descriptive word like “qorashaqshaq”, “olapopishak”, “sassiqpopishak”, “olashaqshaq” and the etymology of several ornithological terms like “kakku”, “bulbul”, “bedana”, “zogcha”, “zagizgon”, “chumchuq”, “g`ulg`ultovuq”, “go`ngqarg`a” (Kungurov R., in 1966, 113-119).

The dissertation on the theme “Uzbek terminology relating to horse-raising” has made a great contribution to the development of investigating terms associated with cattle-raising, especially horse-raising. In this work Uzbek terms relating to horse-raising are classified into 12 lexic-semantic groups as:

1. Terms which give the common meaning of “horse”: - “ot”, “at”, “asp”, “takovar”.
2. Terms indicating the gender of a horse: “urg`ochi”, “baytal”, “biya” – (a female horse), “ayg`ir” – (a male horse).
3. Terms describing the species of a horse: “akhaltaka”, “sofqonliarabi” (an Arabian horse with pure blood), “arabi”(Arabian), “salt miniluvchi tip”, “yovmudi”, “sahro tipi”(a horse living in the desert), “o`rmon tipi”(a horse living in the forest), “janubiy tip” (a horse living in the southern areas).
4. Terms expressing the age of a horse: “do`nan”, “g`unajinbiya”(a young female horse), “enabiya” (a horse that has brought a colt), “qulun”, “qulunchoq” (a colt).
5. Terms describing the colour and special features of a horse:” jiyron”(red-haired), “to`riq”, “samanto`riq”, “saman” (light brown), “chovkar/chavkar”, “qo`ng`ir”(brown), “timqora”(jet-black), “bo`z”(grey), “ola”(skewbald horse), “oqto`riq”, “bo`zchipor”, “burulqashqa”, “oq dog”(white spots).
6. Terms describing different processes and events in a horse-raising: “juftlash” (to couple), “o`zarourchitish” (propagate mutually), “uzoqqarindoshlikurchitish”(propagate distant relatives), “chatishtirish” (breed), “boqish”(feed), “asrash” (keep), “qulunlash” (give birth), “yo`rtish”, “yo`rg`alash” (amble, pace), “sakrabchopish”.

7. Terms relating to horse sports and competitions: “ko`pkari”, “qizquvish”, “papakho`yin”, “olomonpoyga”, “chogan”.

8. Terms indicating horse names: “saman”, “jiyron”, “bars”, “ko`kkaptar”, “qoplon”, “chibor”, “yo`rg`a”, “uchqur”, “qizbel”, “asov”, “yurtoqi”.

9. Terms relating to people whose job is connected with horse-raising: “chorvador” (a cattle-raiser), “yilqichi” (a horse-raiser), “otboqar” (a horse-holder), “says/sayis”, “jilovdor” (a horse holder), “otliq” (a horse-rider), “suvori/suvoriy” (a cavalry man), “jokey”, “oto`rgatuvchi” (a horse trainer), “taqachi” (a farrier), “miroxur”, “biyaboqar” (a horse-herder), “toyboqar” (a horse-herder).

10. Terms describing the places where horses are kept and fed: “qo`ra” (a court yard), “og`il” (a cattle shed), “yaylov” (summer pasture), “bostirma” (shed), “toykhona”, “otkhona”, “jilovkhona”, “okhur” – (crib, manger).

11. Terms indicating the items for horses: “juga/yuga”, “egar” (saddle), “jilov” (rein), “qorinbog”, “pushtan/pushton”, “ayil”, “quyushqon”, “abzal/jabduq” (harness), “bellik”, “zul”, “jul”. (Usmonov S, 1988, 6-14).

S. Usmonov`s work challenges other researchers to study zoonims as well as ornithological terms classifying into small lexic-semantic groups in the future.

Z. Mirkholikov studied lexical-semantic and grammatical peculiarities of fish names. (Mirkholikov Z. M., 1991, 6-15). In this dissertation it was paid a great attention to the principles of giving names to fishes, the peculiarities of the original and borrowed terms relating to fish. R. Safarova studied zoonims which are in active usage in Uzbek from the point of gender-species view and analysed 6 distinctive semas:

1. according to their colour;
2. according to their physical features;
3. according to their immature species;
4. according to their biological gender;
5. according to their wildness and domesticated features;
6. according to the speed of growing. (Safarova R., in 1990.Safarova R., in 1996, 28-29).

Since the Proclamation of the Independence several studies have been carried in the field of lexicology of cattle-raising as well as birds` names systematically. For instance, P. Safarov paid attention to the analysis of several ornithological terms such as “g`oz” (goose), ”tovuq” (hen), ”khuroz” (cock), ”o`rdak” (duck), while investigating lexicon of animal names based on the history of Uzbek grammar (P. Safarov., in 1992, 4-17).

H. Saidova recommends such order while arranging animal names which are in common usage in Uzbek monolingual dictionary:

- a) The word itself;

- b) Direct semantic definition of the word;
- c) Its metaphorical meaning;
- d) Its onomastic usage;
- e) Terminological definition from the point of biology.

According to her, when one follows the order above to give definitions of zoonims the word can be put contrary to the term, then the relationship of words is noticed and the formation of a word from the others is seen. (Saidova H., in 1995, 4-20). H. Saidova analyses some ornithological terms like "burgut" (eagle), "tovus" (peacock), "to`ti" (parrot), "musicha" (dove), "chumchuq" (sparrow), "qarg`a" (crow), "lochin" (falcon) to describe people based on the principle mentioned above (Saidova H., in 2001, 81-83). B. Abdushukurov analysed terms relating to birds` names dividing into 7 small groups. (Abdushukurov B., in 1998, 4-18).

B. Zaripov studies the role of some ornithological terms in making different poetry styles in his dissertation. Afterwards the scientist had the manual named "Descriptive means of literature" and a scientific brochure "Zoonims in A. Navoi`s works" published based on his earlier research. (Zaripov B., in 2002, Zaripov B., in 2007). L. Abdullaeva analyses the metaphorical usage of some ornithological terms such as: "qarchig`ay", "burgut" (eagle), "musicha" (dove), "tovuq" (hen), "boyqush", (owl) in literature and creating metaphors in her monograph named "The lexical methodology of Uzbek literature" (Abdullaeva L., in 1979, 43-62). While learning animals` names in "Boburnoma" a well-known scientist of geography, professor H. Hasanov mentioned in his book "Zahiriddin Muhammad Bobur" that birds` names such as "tovus"(peacock), "qurotu" (bedana-quail), "to`ti" (parrot), "shorak" (mayna - starling), "lo`cha" (baqalamun, khurozcha - rooster), "durroj" (a type of partridge), "pul-paykar" (a partridge living in the mountains), "sahroitovuq "(a hen living in the deserts), "chilsiy" (a type of partridge), "shom" (bankivkhuroz- a type of cock), "kharchal" (tuvaloq), "charz" (bizg`aldoq), "bag`riqora and other birds living near the water such as: "ding" (hindilaylak – an Indian stork), "mayin" (oqbo`yinlaylak- a stork with white neck), "laklak" (laylak – a stork), "soras" (tevturna – a type of a crane), "ulug` bo`zak", (ibis), "oqbo`zak" (ibis), "o`rdak" (duck), "zumaj", "sor" (qizilkalkhat- a red kite), "olaqarg`a" (crow), "murg`ljangal" (tustovuq - pheasant), "ulug` shappara", "akka" (hakka, zag`izg`on - magpie), "kurak", "(qorajarqaldirg`och" (a type of swallow), "quyil" (kakku - cacao) are given. (Hasanov H., in 1966, 69). The same bird species are written in the pamphlet "Bobur is a linguist" by professor B. Urinboev. (Urinboev B., in 1993, 19). In "Dictionary of birds from A. Navoi`s works more than 80 birds` names are mentioned such as "anqo" (a bird in myths), "burgut" (eagle), "zog`" (jackdaw), "qarg`a" (crow) and their meanings are given with examples from the poet`s works.

In his etymologic dictionary professor Sh. Rahmatullaev gave his significant opinions about the origin and development of about 20 ornithological terms (Rahmatullaev Sh., in 2000, Rahmatullaev Sh., in 2003, Rahmatullaev Sh., in 2009).

There are very few facts about birds' names in the Uzbek language in the book by D. Kh. Bozorova (Bazarava D. Kh., in 1978), in some dialectal and etymologic dictionaries (O'KhShL, in 1971, Rahmatullaev Sh., in 2000, Rahmatullaev Sh., in 2003, Rahmatullaev Sh., in 2009), in some articles (Bazarava D. Kh., in 1975, 11-12; Bazarava D. Kh., in 1975, 96-100; Is'hoqov F., in 1973, 43-50, Nosirov Sh., in 1986, 56-60, Nizomkhonov H., in 1993, in 1993, 67-71; Normurodov R., in 2008, 97-100; Suvonova R., in 2009, 102-105; Kulakhmedov E., in 2009, 145-147; Normurodov R., in 2010, 109-118 and so on). The usage of birds' names in Uzbek literature, and the similarities, polysemic features of those names and their lexical-grammatical and semantic analysis are done in the specific ornithological literatures, and literary dictionaries mentioned by D. Kh. Bozorova in her book about birds' names. It is of a great importance for being a unique monograph studying and analyzing birds' names in the Uzbek language for the first time. (Bazarava D. Kh., in 1978, 28-133).

In his book named "Modern Uzbek language" F. Kamol mentioned some birds' names such as "qush" (bird), "tovuq" (hen), "g'oz" (goose), "o'rdak" (duck), "bulduruq", "lochin" (falcon), "qarg'a" (crow), "turna" (crane), etc while stating the words in the noun category which is one of the main parts of the vocabulary fund of the language. Moreover, words existing in Uzbek lexicons which are common to all Turkish languages are analyzed by classifying them into more than ten small lexical-semantic groups. One of such small lexical-semantic groups is named as "Words describing animals and birds" and one can see some ornithological terms such as "qush" (bird), "tovuq" (hen), "qarg'a" (crow), "g'oz" (goose), "o'rdak" (duck), "bedana" (quail) in it. (in 1957, 57-92).

In the research work named "Lexicology of the Uzbek language" Turkish lexical system in the modern Uzbek language are classified into several lexical-thematic groups and there "Birds and the names of their body parts are shown precisely and some birds' names and names of their body parts are stated: "bulduruq", "bo'ktargi", "burgut" (eagle), "tovuq" (hen), "tuvaloq", "turna" (crane), "to'rg'ay" (lark), "ukki" (owl), "chumchuq" (sparrow), "shunqor" (hawk), "o'rdak" (duck), "qaldirg'och" (swallow), "qanot" (wing), "tumshuq" (beak), "qarqara" (heron), "qarg'a" (crow), "qirg'iy", "qirg'ovul" (pheasant), "quzg'un" (raven), "quyruq" (tail), "qarchig'ay", "qumri", "qush" (bird) and so on. (Uzbek language, in 1981, 68-69).

Professor E. Begmatov divides Uzbek words into 28 thematic groups in his book "Lexical groups of modern Uzbek literary language". One of these groups is called "Birds' names" and there are ornithological terms as following: "bulduruq", "bo'ktargi", "burgut" (eagle), "tovuq" (hen), "tuvaloq", "turna" (crane), "to'rg'ay" (lark), "ukki" (owl), "chumchuq" (sparrow), "shunqor" (hawk), "o'rdak" (duck), "qaldirg'och" (swallow), "qanot" (wing), "tumshuq" (beak), "qarqara" (heron), "qarg'a" (crow), "qirg'iy", "qirg'ovul" (pheasant), "quzg'un" (raven), "quyruq" (tail), "qarchig'ay", "qumri" and so on. Moreover, in this work "birds' names and terms describing their organism" are stated as a separate group: "tumshuq" (beak), "qanot" (wings), "changal" (claw), "quyruq" (tail) and so on. (Begmatov E., in 1985, 121-125).

The history of Uzbek dialects shows that in research studies done by K.K. Yudakhin, A.K. Borovkov, V.V. Reshetov, SH. Shoabdurahnonov, F. Abdullaev, S. Ibrohimov, M. Mirzaev, O. Madrahimov, Kh. Doniyorov, N. Rajabov, K. Muhammadjonov, A. Aliev, A. Ishaev, A. Shermatov, E. Urazov, B. Juraev, Sh. Nosirov, S. Rahimov, E. Sheraliev, N. Murodova, N. Shoimova and by other dialecticians, several birds' names are mentioned as an illustrative material. We are absolutely delighted to state that the early investigations on Uzbek dialectal ornithology were conducted by Sh. Nosirov. At first the scholar gave some opinions about the usage and the lexical-semantic and phonetic peculiarities of some birds' names such as "zag'izg'on", "hakka" (magpie), "olashaqshaq", "chumchq" (sparrow), "chittak" (titmouse), "go'ngqarg'a" (a type of crow), based on facts taken from Uzbek dialects in his article issued in the journal "The Uzbek language and literature" (Nosirov Sh., in 1986, 56-60). Afterwards Sh. Nosirov worked further on this article and included it in the research "The lexicon of Uzbek dialects" (Nosirov Sh., in 1991, 120-180). Z. Kholmedova stated some birds' names such as "qush" (bird), "kukukpsh" (qizilishton -woodpecker), "ko`bakchay", "qarg'a" (crow), "aldqarg'a", "ko`kqarg'a" (a blue crow), "qaraqarg'a" (a black crow), "to`rg'ay" (lark), "mullato`rg'ay" (a type of lark), used in the Karnok dialect which one of the dialects spoken by the Uzbeks living in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, while studying the lexicon of this dialect. (Kholmedova Z., in 2006, 6-8)

In several textbooks and manuals of Zoology, a number of birds' names, their usage and alternatives in Russian and Latin are taught. For example, there is a special tome "Birds" in "Encyclopedia of Zoology" by an academician T. Zohidov. Besides birds names in Uzbek and Latin, there is a great deal of valuable information about their conditions, geographical locations, living territories, propagating (breeding), eating habits, some biological features and their importance in people's lives. (Zohidov T., in 1957, 7-127). In the book "The animal world of Uzbekistan by O. Bogdanov there is significant information about the habitats, lifestyles, and practical value of approximately 100 bird species. (Bogdanov O.R., in 1965, 89-205). In the textbook "Zoology" for the pupils of 6-7th grades, the birds which can be seen in our country are classified as local birds, nomadic birds, emigrating birds and immigrating ones, there are data about more than 50 bird families such as Passeridae or Emberizidae, Corvidae, Phasinidae, and so on. (Mavlonov O.M., Komilov G., in 2000, 233-289).

The formation and the development of Uzbek ornithological terms have become known for the sake of a great number of scientists' studies such as "Animals in rural areas of Central Asia" by A.A Abdurazzakov, (1958), "forests and reserves of Uzbekistan" by M. Isamuhammedov, M. Koriev (1972), "Natural Geography of central Asia" by M. Koriev (1968), "the animal world of Uzbekistan" by O.P. Bogdanov (1965), "Footprints of animals and birds" by A. Lesnyak (1966), "rare birds and mammals of Uzbekistan" by O.P. Bogdanov (1968), "There is a life even in the desert" by N. A. Rashkevich (1961), "the animal world of Uzbekistan" by B. A. Moiseev and D. Yu. Koshkarov (1990), "birds are our friends" by E. Ravshanov (2010).

E. F. Ishberdin's dissertations, articles and monographs are considered the primary work in the field of investigating birds' names as a separate thematic group. (Ishberdin E.F., 1969, Ishberdin E.F., 1973, 142-160, Ishberdin E.F., 1986). But the researcher studied only a few dialectal forms of ornithological lexicon in the work mentioned above. Some data about the etymology of ornithological terms common in all Turkish languages is given in the dissertations done by D.S. Setorova, M.M. Ginatullin, and E.I. Safina. (Setorova D.S., 1971; Ginatullin M.M., 1973; Safina E.I., 2005). And K. Ibragimov gives some information about the etymology of some birds' names used in ancient Turkish and studies their usage in modern Turkish languages in his article and dissertation (Ibragimov K., 1974, 37-47; Ibragimov K., 1975).

In conclusion, some studies have been carried out in the field of investigating ornithological terms in the Turkish languages, especially in Uzbek lexicology. However, lexical-semantic and methodological peculiarities of ornithological terms from the point of system lexicology have not been studied so far. As Sh. Nosirov mentioned: "Studying birds' names is the field which has been the least investigated by now, as a consequence of which different bird species have the same names or there are different names for a bird. Some birds' names are not included in literary language or their literary norms are not assigned clearly for not having been studied thoroughly". (Nosirov Sh., 1991, 177). And this urges us to conduct a special monographic study on the lexicon of this branch.

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